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CHANGING TO THE BETTER? EXPERIENCES FROM TURNING A HANDS-ON INNOVATION COURSE INTO AN ONLINE COURSE

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ABSTRACT

During the times of Covid-19 and the different degrees of lockdowns, we had to rethink central elements in a hands-on experiential course on innovation and cross-disciplinary teamwork, turning it into a fully online course or blending a few physical campus activities with online elements.

In this concept paper, we report on and reflect on our experiences, experiments, and learnings from transforming a hands-on experiential course on innovation and cross-disciplinary teamwork into a fully online course or blending a few physical campus activities with online elements during the Covid 19 lockdown.

The paper builds on three full course runs from spring 2020, summer 2020, winter 2020, and a fourth run started up in spring 2021.

Our experience, challenges, experiments, learnings, and reflections are organized into six themes; prototypes and prototyping, collaboration within the team, collaboration with external partners and data collection, online team formation, the facilitation process, and the presentation of the solution to the company.

Among others, the results include experiences like this: Without having access to campus and workshops, the students worked with a broader range of prototypes and

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created more of them during the innovation process. This experience draws more attention to the prototyping process than the prototype itself and highlights the learning potential for more iterations than just one version of the solution. The paper includes similar examples and reflections for all six themes.

We discuss what we can learn from these experiences and which elements are relevant to maintain and develop further in a post-corona setup. The discussion also includes which initiatives are needed to support further development and implementation of these elements both from a course organizing perspective and a learning-enhancing perspective.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

During Covid-19 and the different degrees of lockdowns, we – a teaching and organizing team of three - had to rethink central elements in a hands-on experiential learning course on innovation and cross-disciplinary teamwork and turn it into a fully online course or blending a few physical campus activities with online elements.

Experiential learning is about learning from experience and training skills through actions and reflection on the experience [1]. This is a learning process that is designed for the students to learn from natural consequences, mistakes and successes and emphasizes the opportunities for the students to take initiatives and learn by doing by being actively involved in the experience [2],[3]. During the lockdown the conditions for ensuring this was clearly challenges and limited.

This concept paper report on and reflect over our experiences, experiments, and learnings from this transformation. The paper builds on three full course runs from spring 2020, summer 2020, winter 2020, and a fourth run started up in spring 2021.

Our experiences, challenges, experiments, learnings, and reflections are organized into six themes; prototypes and prototyping, collaboration within the team, collaboration with external partners and data collection, online team formation, the facilitation process, and the presentation of the solution to the company.

1) Prototypes and prototyping in an online setting. Not having access to campus and workshops, we saw the students using a broader range of prototypes and creating more of them during the innovation process. This experience draws more attention to the prototyping process than the prototype itself.

2) The lockdowns created a need for finding new ways of collaborating within the student teams. The students could not meet in person, which naturally entailed moving the teamwork to online platforms. This draws attention to how teamwork and student learning can be supported in a (partially) online environment.

3) When not being able to meet in person, both students and participating company partners had to be creative to arrange company visits, user interviews, and observations, and so forth. This experience opened up to new types of collaboration being more independent of time and place due to online collaborations

4) Online team formation emphasizing diversity, team roles, competencies, and motivation still had to be carried out despite limitations on the number of students who could meet physically. This challenged the pre-Covid19 set up in the course. The course coordinators had to experiment with different online group formation formats.

5) Changes in the way the facilitation process unfolded due to an online or partially online format. A key element in the course is the facilitation of teamwork by collaboration with teaching assistants and lecturers. Moving this to an online format created several challenges concerning the level and the depth of interaction with the different teams.

6) A final experience has been concerned with changing the delivery format of the student's solution to the company. Here it was decided to move the presentations into a video format instead of a live pitch.

1.2 Course context

The course context for the experiences we report on in this paper is a multidisciplinary innovation course offered to Bachelor of Engineering students at The Technical University of Denmark. The course is a hands-on experiential course involving real-life cases provided by a large number of companies. The course is focused on teaching and training an innovative mind set and enabling students to participate in innovation processes and organize and implement a multidisciplinary innovation process using relevant innovation models and methods. The course is a mandatory element in 18 study programs and placed in the last part of the study programs. [1]

The outline for the course is that the students work in multidisciplinary teams with specific real-life challenges offered by the involved companies. The companies provide open-ended projects, which take a starting point in actual challenges observed by the company. The company is the problem owner, and the students should involve the context reality of the company in solving the challenges. The students are responsible for finding ways to apply their unique skills and knowledge to create value in the projects. [2] Coming from different study programs, the students do often not know each other before forming the teams they work in.

Students are expected to research the problem during the course by doing observations, site visits, and interviews with relevant actors such as users, customers, experts, problem owners, etc. Thus, the course allows for a high degree of interaction and collaboration between students and external partners, but also among students themselves. Moreover, central elements in the course are pitching and prototyping solutions in campus workshops.

Due to the course's interactive, outgoing, and hands-on character, course activities and collaborations were rethought to nevertheless still reach the course's learning goals during lockdown times.

2 METHODOLOGY

The paper builds on three full course runs from spring 2020, summer 2020, fall 2020, and a fourth run started up in spring 2021.

The semester courses (spring and fall) runs once a week for 13 weeks with about 250 –350 students and 20-25 companies. The summer course is an intensive 6-week course with about 150 students and 6 companies.

We have experienced different degrees of lockdown during these four course runs and implemented many initiatives and refinements in response to the lockdown situation. Since the first lockdown, lectures, meetings, supervisions, etc., have been offered online, making it possible to follow and participate in the course online; however, some sessions have been offered physical whenever possible with an online option.

A summary is below:

Course Term	Lock Down	Initiatives
Spring 2020	Startup as usual Complete lockdown halfway through the semester	Online collaboration in teams and with external partners Video pitch Online DEMO Day Prototyping with no access to workshops
Summer 2020	No lockdown Social distancing and restrictions on gathering (max 50 people together)	Group formation: face-to-face combined with preselection and questionnaires Mixed collaboration (online/physical) in teams and with external partners Video pitch Online DEMO Day Prototyping with limited or no access to workshops
Fall 2020	No lockdown Social distancing and restrictions on gathering (max 50 people together) Lockdown by the end of the semester	Group formation: face-to-face combined with preselection and questionnaires Mixed collaboration (online/physical) in teams and with external partners Formal and pre-scheduled facilitation meetings Video pitch Online DEMO Day

		Prototyping with limited or no access to workshops
Spring 2021	Lockdown throughout the course. Limited re-opening by the end of the course.	Online group formation Online collaboration in teams and with external partners Formal and pre-scheduled facilitation meetings Video pitch Online DEMO Day Prototyping with limited access to workshops

The paper focuses on lessons learned and identifies patterns in our experiences rather than a detailed analysis of the implemented initiatives. In the section below, we report on the experiences from the different types of initiatives.

3 RESULTS

In the following sections, we will briefly go through our significant observations and experiences emerging from the transition from a physical to an online format of the course.

3.1 Prototypes and Prototyping

During the close-downs, the students had little or no access to campuses and the workshops and labs. This challenged the students' work with prototyping and prototypes. Developing prototypes is a critical element in the course as the students are expected to develop prototypes and use the prototypes to test and validate their solutions with users and other stakeholders. In the pre-covid-19 setup, the students would often spend considerable time in the prototype lab creating elaborate prototypes - 3D-printing was a preferred tool for creating prototypes. There would often be several iterations involved in the prototyping process - both from user feedback and working with the prototype itself.

Limited or no access to workshops and labs forced the students to change how they worked with prototypes and prototyping. To a large extent, we observed that students moved away from developing physical prototypes and began to develop "simpler" prototypes using digital and virtual means. In many cases, these digital and virtual prototypes were simpler and more focused on the customers' general use instead of demonstrating concrete product features. Furthermore, as discussed later in the paper, the students were also forced to engage with users and other stakeholders in non-physical manners due to covid-19 restrictions. These

developments resulted in the students developing a larger number of prototypes and engaging users in new digital ways. The students were able to spend more time validating their prototypes instead of refining the prototypes

3.2 New ways of collaborating within the teams

As a result of the close-downs and the associated limits on the number of students who could meet, they had to find new ways of collaborating within their teams. The students quickly managed to move their activities to different digital platforms – for example, Zoom, MS Teams, and Discord. Naturally, many teams needed time to adjust to the new situation. However, most teams were able to continue their teamwork without significant disruptions.

Not being able to meet physically created many challenges for the teams concerning collaboration and coordination. Before the covid-19 lockdown, a lot of collaboration and coordination was done informally during the physical teamwork at the campus. The teams had to focus more on a structured approach to the distribution of work within the teams and also on following up on this. Many teams had to formalize their work processes, knowledge sharing, and coordination mechanisms. This formalization entailed using project management tools to keep track of activities, using log-books to capture major events and insights, and appointing a project manager. In many teams, this role of project manager was temporary and shifted from week to week. Finally, the groups that had spent time together during the start of the course found it easier to shift to digital collaboration.

3.3 Working with external partners in new ways

The third observation concerns the collaboration with external partners and informants. A vital element of the course is that the students and their teams should "get out of the building" to meet their company contacts, users, customers, experts, and so forth. Furthermore, the students should ideally do user observations as well as testing their solutions with prospective users. This collaboration is considered essential for the quality of the solutions developed by the students. Furthermore, the collaboration with external partners is vital for the knowledge creation by the students during their work on the company challenges.

Again, not meeting in person challenged this interaction. Data collection from external partners was difficult. Our observations have shown that the students managed to migrate to new formats for collaborating independent of time and place by drawing on digital platforms. However, the limited "bandwidth" connected with digital interaction provided challenges in some cases. It was not easy to do observations and interact closely with users. As discussed, in connection with prototyping, it was more challenging to get feedback from users. It also proved to be difficult to engage some users due to concerns about the risk of infection. Finally, it was observed that it is easier for users to dismiss contacts from student teams when they were being approached through a digital channel. The "depth" of answers from and discussions with external partners seemed to become smaller when using a digital platform for the interaction. On the other hand, some teams also found they

could reach out to a larger and more diverse group of external partners as they were unbound by time and place. Social Media Platforms were used more to reach and engage the users. Some companies managed to run live video feeds of a walkthrough of their production, replacing physical meetings.

3.4 Online team formation

In non-covid times the course commenced with a team formation process whereby the students selected which company challenge to work on and formed teams of 5-6 students. This process was a physical process where all students were present and interacted with each other. A key element in the team formation was a "speed-dating" process to physically meet fellow students they did not know beforehand. It is a requirement for the team formation that the students form inter-disciplinary teams with a maximum of two students from the same study line. As part of the team formation process, the students should also align their expectations to their desired grade in the course and discuss their professional and personal competencies.

The covid-19 restrictions forced the course coordinators to rethink this interactive process and change it to an online format. In this online format, the student firstly would pick the company challenge they would prefer to work on. Following this, the students should form teams. Here the students were to fill in a digital tag with their name, personality type based on the Meyers Briggs test (for example, ISTP-I), preferred team role (based on a Belbin test), task preference (product, technology, project management, team or business), and line of study. The students were then asked to place their tags in an online document (in MS Teams). The course's facilitators supervised the process to ensure that the formal requirements were met, i.e., that the teams were interdisciplinary and that there was an appropriate mix of personality types and team roles within the teams. This online process of team formation proved to be successful, and it did relieve some of the stress that had been associated with the in-person pre-covid-19 physical team formation processes. We have not observed any differences in the teams and the quality of their work due to this change in the team formation process. There has not been observed an increase in the amount of conflict within the teams either.

3.5 The facilitation process

The fifth observation is concerned with the facilitation process. In the pre-covid-19 runs of the course, facilitation has largely been ad-hoc and informal - student teams and facilitators interacting several times a day, often due to the facilitator dropping in on a team. Naturally, there have formal meetings between facilitators and teams in connection with critical milestones. However, most of the contact was based on both teams and facilitators being present at campus and the opportunities for interaction created by this. During covid-19, the opportunities for physical interaction became limited and non-existent at some points in time.

The meeting activities between teams and facilitators (both the formal and the informal) had to move online. A key observation from the facilitators was that many student teams were reluctant to interact with facilitators ad hoc online, and the

facilitators often lost track of the teams as they moved their activities to digital platforms outside the ones recommended by the course coordinators – activities were moved to, for example, Discord or Miro. As such, the facilitation process needed to be formalized, and it has been necessary to increase the number of scheduled meetings with the teams significantly to compensate for the loss of informal ad-hoc interactions at the campus.

3.6 Changing the delivery format

A final element, which has been changed as the result of covid-19, is the delivery format. Usually, the students would present their solution in a joint public poster session where the team would show/demonstrate their solution and in a pitch session where the team would pitch their solution to a panel including facilitators and company representatives. These sessions would entail that up to 300 persons were gathered in on location. It has therefore been necessary to rethink these sessions. It was decided to transform the delivery format to video.

The poster session has been replaced with a video gallery where all teams upload a short video pitch presenting their solution. The video gallery is in a closed you-tube channel which only is open to the persons involved in the course. The pitch session has been maintained, even though it has been transformed into an online format where teams show their video pitch and receive feedback on their solution. It has been observed that the teams approach the task of producing a video in a variety of ways – some teams use a PowerPoint presentation with voice over other teams are making small films of very high quality. This change in the course has, in general, been well received by all involved in the course. Creating videos is a valuable skill for the students since more and more content on the internet is videos.

3.7 Summary of the results

In the table below, our observations have been summarized.

Table 1. Summary of the results

Element:	Observations:
Prototypes and prototyping	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Simpler and more digital prototypes- Increased focus on the overall use of the solution- Less focus on detailed product features
Collaborating within the teams	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Easy to move collaboration to digital platforms- More formalization and structure within the project work
Working with external partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Difficult to establish a close collaboration with external partners- Lacking depth in answers from external contacts- Possible to reach out to a larger and more diverse group of externals, especially through Social Media channels

Team formation	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Successfully moved to a digital format- Digital format less stressful for some students- No increase in conflicts within the teams
Facilitation process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- More structured (less ad-hoc) facilitation process- Increase in formalized meetings
Delivery format	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Successful change to a video pitch format

4 DISCUSSION

At first sight, transferring a hands-on experimental course into an online course with limited physical interaction between students, external partners, and stakeholders, and only limited access to workshops, seemed like an emergency action that would usually call for cancellation.

However, to our own surprise the result was better than expected especially with regard to the course's practice-oriented nature. It showed that going online and introducing more digital tools opened up to new ways of collaborating, to new learnings and to new ways of accessing empirical data and knowledge in the student teams and project work.

Many of the initiatives that was developed and introduced during these four "pandemic" course runs, will be maintained and developed further in the future course runs as well as looking more in to the students' experience and learning outcomes due to these changes. Especially looking more into our observations on prototypes and prototyping and the shift in focus from the (technical) prototype to the prototyping process and the overall solution when access to workshops was limited. The team formation process and use of the digital format is also worth looking more into with regards to how it can support the students awareness of own role in a team and the general discomfort many students experience with team formation processes.

During the past year many new experiences and experiments with online teaching have been made. In this case being forced to go online and rethink the course has been a welcome provocation and a nice opportunity to break away from existing behaviors and idiosyncrasies on how to teach and train innovation, and try out new learning elements that we otherwise might have postponed or been reluctant to.

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